

Can Time Be Reversed? Information, irreversibility, and a misplaced paradox

Why can I not reconstruct a broken egg, so it is identical to the one before the accident? Nobody ever experienced reversal of such an event (unless they did not admit it...). Time obediently flows always in one direction, and physicists call it the "arrow of time". It is not a law of physics, only an observation of the fact which regulates functioning of the whole Universe...

The second law of thermodynamics has suspiciously a lot to do with the arrow's existence. *Nota bene* - something curious. While in English it is a "thermodynamics law", in e.g. Polish it is called a "rule". Polish is here closer to the truth. The second law has never been proven - however, nobody ever saw it breaking down (at least until now...).

The majority of the physics laws operate equally well if time flows forward or backward - on the condition that they describe microscopic phenomena in closed systems. Let's look at any closed macroscopic process - it runs through a sequence of such steps; so, thanks to the time-reversible equations we can always predict which way it evolves, regardless the time direction. This would seem to imply that time is symmetrical; the arrow has disappeared...

Here we run into a paradox. In our open macroscopic reality, all observed processes are time-irreversible. Why? How to explain that all we see defies the proven statistical thermodynamics? This question is at the heart of the Loschmidt's paradox; we will come back to it.

Let's try one of the science's favoured exorcisms for fighting paradoxes - a thought experiment. Let's take a real, common event - a living cell in which a new protein undergoes the folding process which will yield its highly organized, functional structure. Our system at the beginning comprises the unfolded protein and the surrounding it molecules. The number of possible positions and speeds of all the molecules involved is astronomical. This is the key moment - to describe what has happened we need to have complete, precise knowledge.

Well? Each microscopic step towards the final product is not unique. The process is so complicated, the number of accessible microstates so astronomical that the identical product can be realized via many different routes. The problem is that Nature does not have a cameraman registering every process in every corner of the Universe... Information describing what happened is irreversibly lost at each step of the folding process. The scientific name of this, *nomen omen*, obvious phenomenon - "structural underdetermination" - highlights the frustration... We can go from the A to the B in many ways and Nature does not have a method (nor, probably, the need) to remember which path was chosen... Stalemate.

Consequences for our understanding? Painful. The very objective of precise reversal of the arrow of time becomes a wrongly formulated task! To do that we would need to have the knowledge which was never physically recorded anywhere.

Let's shift the perspective and look not at one process concerning one cell but at the whole reality. Everything that is happening never has the universal cameraman around... Structural underdetermination is not a general law of physics or the consequence of our experimental or

mental tools nor any simplifications. It is an intrinsic property of our Universe and the laws which govern it.

As a candy, let's return to the Loschmidt's paradox. His question is: "how is it possible that the irreversible arrow of time observed for each macroscopic process arises from a sequence of reversible microphysical steps?" ... It seems that Loschmidt is right - if in the isolated system there is no loss of local information, the arrow of time is senseless...

However, looking around, his paradox does not disappear; it changes context - the question: "how can from the time-reversible equations emerge the irreversible arrow of time?" does not make sense. The point is - the real, open world does not preserve (for us) the information necessary to reverse the arrow of time...

Does anyone want to build the time machine?

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